

LANGUAGE SYSTEM AND ITS STRUCTURAL FEATURES

The concept of language as a phenomenon of cultural and historical development

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Annotation: *The article examines the reasons of the most important features of speech activity, which distinguishes it from other types of activity. Speech communication is carried out according to the laws of a particular languages.*

Key words: *speech communication, language, psycholinguistics, scientific concepts, mental formation.*

TIL TIZIMI VA UNING TUZILISH XUSUSIYATLARI

Til tushunchasi madaniy-tarixiy taraqqiyot hodisasi sifatida

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada nutq faoliyatining boshqa faoliyat turlaridan ajralib turadigan eng muhim xususiyatlarining sabablari ko'rib chiqiladi. Nutq aloqasi ma'lum bir til qonunlariga muvofiq amalga oshirilishi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *nutq aloqasi, til, psixolingvistika, ilmiy tushunchalar, aqliy shakllanish.*

ЯЗЫКОВАЯ СИСТЕМА И ЕЕ СТРУКТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

Концепция языка как феномен культурно-исторического

Аннотация: *В статье исследуются причины важнейших особенностей речевой деятельности, отличающие ее от других видов деятельности. Речевое общение осуществляется по законам определенного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *Речевое общение, язык, психолингвистика, научные концепции, психическое формирование.*

The language has an internal order, the organization of its parts into a single whole. Consequently, systemic and structural nature characterize the language and its units as a whole from different angles. The language system is an inventory of its units, united in categories and tiers according to typical relations; the structure of the language is formed by relations between tiers and parts of units; therefore, the structure

of a language is only one of the features of a system of language. Language unit, language category, language tier, language relations - these concepts do not coincide, although they are all important for revealing the concept of a language system. Units of a language are its constant elements, differing from each other in purpose, structure and place in the language system. According to their purpose, language units are divided into nominative, communicative and combat. The main nominative unit is the word (lexeme), the communicative unit is the sentence. Structural units of the language serve as a means of constructing and designing nominative and communicative units; the building units are phonemes and morphemes, as well as the forms of words and forms of phrases. Language levels are located in relation to each other according to the principle of ascending or descending complexity of language units. ¹The essence of this phenomenon lies in the preservation of the properties and characteristics of the units of the lower level in the system of the higher level, but in a more perfect form. Thus, the relationship between the levels of the language system is not reducible to a simple hierarchy - subordination or entry. Therefore, it is fair to call a language system a system of systems. Let's consider language units from the point of view of speech flow segmentation. At the same time, a language unit is understood as something that, expressing meaning, materializes in speech segments and their features. Since the speech realization of language units is characterized by a fairly wide range of variability, the mental operation of identification is applied to the selected speech segments, which consists in the fact that formally different speech segments are recognized as the material embodiment of the same language unit. The basis for this is the commonality of the meaning expressed by the varying units or the function they perform. The beginning of the segmentation of the speech flow is the allocation of communicative units in its statements or phrases. In the language system, it corresponds to a syntaxeme or syntactic model representing the syntactic level of the language. The next stage of segmentation is the division of statements into word forms, in which several heterogeneous functions (nominative, derivational and relative) are combined, so the identification operation is carried out separately for each direction.

The vocabulary of a particular language forms a lexical level. A class of word forms that has the same word-formation meaning constitutes a word-formation type a derivative. The class of word forms with identical formative affixes is identified in a grammatical form a grammar. The next stage of segmentation of the speech flow is to identify the smallest significant units' morphs. Morphs with identical lexical roots and grammatical functional and affixal meanings are combined into one language unit a

¹ Potebnya A.A. *Comparative stylistics of professional speech based on the material of the Russian and French languages*. M: Librokom, 2009. 144 p

morpheme.¹ The whole set of morphemes of a given language forms a morpheme level in the language system. Thus, the allocation of a level or subsystem of a language is allowed when: the subsystem has the basic properties of the language system as a whole; the subsystem meets the requirement of constructability, that is, the units of the subsystem serve to construct units of the subsystem of a higher organization and are isolated from them; the properties of the subsystem are qualitatively different from the properties of the units of the underlying subsystem constructing it; a subsystem is determined by a language unit that is qualitatively different from the units of adjacent subsystems. The peculiarity of the level model of the language system is the desire to present the language as a symmetrical and ideally ordered scheme. The most remarkable property of language structure is the ability to construct an infinite number of means of communication sentences from a finite supply of elements in other way is words. Outside of language, every symbolic means of communication is the horn signal, the road sign, the republican elephant is an isolated case. However, when teaching their native language, no one has to memorize one sentence after another of the language. Instead, a potentially infinite variety of sentences are constructed according to rules that determine how words can be combined in a sentence. There are two kinds of rules. The syntax rules determine which combinations of units are allowed. So, for English, the combination Article + Name + Intransitive verb makes an acceptable sentence for example: The boy fell “The boy fell”, but the combination Verb + Name + Article + Preposition does not, for example: ran boy the on. Semantic rules determine how the meaning of a more complex structure (syntactic group or sentence) is derived from the meanings and organization syntax of its constituent words. The complex and at the same time systemic nature of the language is clearly manifested in elements smaller than syntactic units, and even smaller than words. Words themselves have a complex structure, and a certain regularity is inherent in this device. Language thus exhibits a hierarchical organization in which the units of every level, except the lowest, are added up, according to certain regular patterns, from the units of the lower level.² Specific sections of linguistics study the different levels of this hierarchy and the interaction of these levels with each other. Phonology studies the elementary sounds of a language and their combinations. Morphology is the study of the morphemes of a language and their compatibility. Syntax studies the formation of phrases (syntactic groups) and sentences. Semantics has to deal with the meanings of morphemes and words, and the various ways in which the meanings of larger units are constructed from the meanings of smaller units. There is no consensus on how exactly

¹ Mokienko V.M. *Riddles of Russian phraseology. M.: Higher school, 2010.436 p*

² Dubenets E.M. *Linguistic changes in modern English. Moscow: Glossa-Press, 2003.256 p.*

the structure of a language should be represented. The method of representation proposed here is one of the simplest; many experts believe that more sophisticated ways of representing are needed. However, whatever the details of certain descriptions, linguists agree that language is a complex system organized in such a way that, having mastered some observable set of elements and the rules for their combination, a person acquires the ability to produce and understand an unlimited number of specific messages. In the process of learning a language, it is stratified ("stratified") into subsystems of ever smaller ranks up to microsystems. The largest subsystems are called tiers (levels) of the language. In most languages, their phonetic-phonological, morphological, lexical, syntactic. These subsystems meet the requirements of the tiers because the structural-functional (invariant) units by which they are represented (phonemes, morphemes, lexemes, sentences) are in hierarchical relations with each other. This type of relationship is naturally inherent in the tiers themselves, which gives reason to consider language as a system of systems. The study of language as a system-structural formation is the main task of linguistics, because everything that distinguishes languages from each other is ultimately determined by the specific features of the system-structural organization of elements inherent in specific languages.

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